

Assessment of Reclaimed Steel Components in Sweden Current status and coming changes

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ABSTRACT

The Swedish construction industry has made efforts to increase its usage of reclaimed steel components as a mean to reduce its environmental impact.

The chosen strategy has been to focus on reclaimed products that can be equated with new constituent products in a normal design and manufacturing process.

Reclaimed material can be considered as an alternative steel grade in the European regulatory framework. For this, EN 1090-2 requires that relevant properties are known which calls for both reliable and economical assessment methods.

The industry guidelines MVR BS04:2021 were developed to meet this need. It proposes to sort components in test units and relies on a combination of nondestructive and destructive testing for the quality assessment. Four protocols are defined with different requirements levels based on the available information on and the production year of the components.

Typically, components with known provenance produced after 1971 are grouped in a test units and their hardness values are checked. Thereafter the member with the lowest hardness is destructively tested and the results are assigned to all members of the test unit.

MVR BS04:2021 is now widely used and a few examples of recent projects are given here. Traditional stockholders are the main actors providing assessed reclaimed steel at the same price level as new steel. Reclaimed components are sourced when possible and stocked. Some EPD is now available as proof of the environmental benefits and the assessment process can be independently certified.

The upcoming CEN/TS 1090-201 will supersede MVR BS04:2021. It is in principle very similar and only introduces minor changes that should be easy to implement in a Swedish context.

With increasing demand there now is a need to widen the scope of the assessment, fabrication and design methods to include more reclaimed product types, e.g. steel from other sources, welded products and products with minor defects.

Keywords: reuse, reclaimed steel, quality assessment

1 INTRODUCTION

Steel is a circular material which is recycled to a very large extent and steel construction products are increasingly made of recycled scrap steel which have a much lower environmental impact than products made directly from iron ore.

The environmental impact can be even further decreased if the product itself, rather than the material, becomes more circular. The global warming potential (GWP) of a reclaimed steel product is only about one tenth that of the same new product made of recycled material.

This potential of reclaimed products has been known to the industry and increasing reuse has thus been identified as an important strategy to reduce buildings climate impact and meet upcoming environmental regulations.

Besides the need for new practices a key factor to increase the amount of reuse today is the possibility to reliably and economically assess the properties of the reclaimed components and ensure their quality.

This paper presents the strategies for reuse and recent evolution of practices for the assessment of reclaimed steel components in the construction sector in Sweden. It also gives some background to the development of a European Technical Specification for steel reuse and highlights the differences between the two.

2 THE SWEDISH STRATEGY AND PRACTICE FOR CONSTRUCTION STEEL REUSE

2.1 Historical background

In 2018 the Development Fund of the Swedish Construction Industry (*Svenska Byggbranschens Utvecklingsfond, SBUF*) funded a one year feasibility study with the aim to analyze the potential legal obstacles and investigate the technical possibilities to assess reclaimed steel components (1).

The project consortium included representatives from relevant stakeholders: major contractors, trade associations (MVR and SBI), certification body (Nordcert) and government agency (Boverket).

It was found that there are no formal legal barriers to steel reuse. Both design and execution standards at the European level allow the use of alternative steel grades provided that their properties are known. Even the national application standards support and highlight this possibility.

It was also estimated that the chances of successful and increased reuse are greater if the reused products can be equated with new ones in the normal design and manufacturing processes. This was called integrated reuse and means that focus was placed on such reclaimed products that can be considered as constituent products, i.e. steel profiles and plates as opposed to welded and other fabricated products.

Regarding the technical aspects of assessment, it was recognized that destructive testing is applicable but neither practical nor economical. Therefore nondestructive testing was considered and two methods in particular were investigated: hardness testing as a mean to assess the mechanical properties and portable spectrometry (both X-ray fluorescence and Optical Emission Spectrometry) to analyze the chemical composition.

It was concluded that nondestructive testing alone cannot fully replace destructive testing performed in a laboratory. However, nondestructive testing in the field can be part of assessment procedures where costly destructive testing is kept to a minimum. Such assessment procedures were proposed for further investigation.

The initial assessment procedures were further developed with help of a governmental grant (*Boverket*) and successfully implemented in a real construction project in 2020 in Oslo, Norway (2). Finally the industry guidelines were formalized in collaboration with Nordcert and published as a handbook in two parts: MVR BS04:2021 (3). Part 1 is a guide that explains the background to the requirements gathered in part 2.

2.2 Industry guidelines for the assessment of reclaimed steel products as constituent products

2.2.1 Scope

MVR BS04:2021 provides guidelines for the reusability and quality assessment of hot rolled and cold formed profiles in structural steel intended for reuse as constituent products in statically and quasi-statically loaded structures manufactured to EN 1090-2 in execution class EXC1 or EXC2.

Welded products and cold formed sections or sheeting according to EN 1090-4 are not covered.

It is also noted that mechanical fasteners shall not be reused.

Typically the original coating of reclaimed products is removed before fabrication of a new product. Therefore the assessment of existing coatings was not included in the guidelines.

The reclaimed products should not be excessively deformed, corroded or otherwise weakened by holes, notches or cracks. Fire exposure is also seen as ground for rejection.

The assessment of the material quality cannot cover the loading history and therefore reused products shall not be included in the production of new structures submitted to dynamic loads and designed for fatigue. This restriction is explicitly stated but also implicitly enforced by limiting the scope of the guidelines to execution class EXC2.

Note however that it is allowed to reuse products which have been subject to fatigue in the past but are found free from cracks at the time of reuse.

Sweden does not have any seismically active area and how to handle this type of loading and the related fabrication requirements is therefore not a concern.

The guidelines consider reclaimed products as constituent products not covered by the product standards listed in EN 1090-2, even if they initially were manufactured to one of them.

The goal of the assessment procedures is to reliably and economically determine the relevant properties listed in clause 5.1 of EN 1090-2. Among those properties the following are always required:

- Strength (yield and tensile);
- Elongation at failure;
- Tolerances on dimension and shape;
- Heat treatment delivery conditions, and;
- Weldability.

The heat treatment delivery condition is relevant for the distinction between hot formed and cold formed hollow sections which are designed differently in Eurocode. It is implicitly assumed that the profiles geometry, i.e. the size of the corner radius, reveals the type of hollow section.

Weldability is not formally a required property according to EN 1090-2. Nevertheless most customers will expect weldable steel products which is why weldability is considered as a required property. It is declared through the calculation of a carbon equivalent based on the chemical composition of the product.

2.2.2 General principles

The assessment procedures are designed with integrated reuse in mind and intend to determine a steel grade and profile so that the reclaimed product easily can replace an equivalent new product.

The dimensions and relevant tolerances of all reclaimed products are measured and documented. The component can be declared with reference to a standard profile, e.g. HEA200, if all geometrical requirements are fulfilled.

The fundamental principle behind the determination of material properties is that components can be sorted into test units based on their provenance. It is assumed that similar components with regard to their cross section, length and surface treatment which have the same function, e.g. beam or column, in a given structure, do have the same relevant properties and constitute a test unit.

The relevance of this assumption can be investigated by nondestructive testing methods and finally the relevant properties are obtained by one or a few destructive tests and the results are assigned to the whole unit.

The second important principle is that the required amount of testing can be adjusted on the basis of information gathered during prospecting. To this purpose four protocols, A to D, are defined. The appropriate protocol is to be chosen as described by the flowchart below, *Fig. 1*.

Fig. 1. Flowchart for the choice of testing protocol

If the origin of the reclaimed products is unknown, it is not possible to gather several components in a test unit and assign them common properties. In this case, protocol D requires that the components are tested individually with destructive methods. The test results can then be used directly, as characteristic values, or compared to the nominal values in a relevant product standard.

When the provenance of the reclaimed products is known, components can be sorted in test units and nondestructive hardness testing is performed on all members of a test unit to validate the homogeneity of the test unit. Acceptance criteria for the variation of hardness values within a test unit are not explicitly given in the guidelines. They should be determined by procedural tests.

Even nondestructive analysis of the chemical composition can be performed to gather supplementary information on the chemical composition. But it shall not substitute hardness testing.

An important distinction is made with regard to the age of material that is assessed. Components that were produced recently are indeed likely to have properties, including their variability, matching those of current steel grades. These can be assessed on the basis of a single test (Protocol B) whereas a larger statistical basis of at least three tests is necessary to maintain reliability in the assessment of older steels with unknown variability (Protocol C).

Products reclaimed from structures built in or after 1971 are seen as made of modern steel. This cut-off year was chosen as it saw the introduction of steel grades SS-213x that can be compared with today's S355.

When protocol C is applied, the characteristic properties assigned to all members of a valid test unit are based on a statistical analysis of the test results in accordance with the Swedish rules for the application of European design standards (currently EKS 12).

When protocol B is applied, properties assigned to all members of a valid test unit are declared as a reference to a steel grade, e.g. S275, for which the test results fulfill the following criteria in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Acceptance criteria for material strength and ductility

Steel grade	$R_{eH} \geq$ (MPa)	$R_m \geq$ (MPa)	Elongation at fracture ($L_0 = 5,65\sqrt{A_0}$)	R_m/R_{eH}
S235	267	397		
S275	313	452		
S355	391	505	$\geq 14\%$	$\geq 1,10$
S420	463	559		
S460	490	560		

The requirements on yield and ultimate strength represent the 95%-fractiles based on the means and variances given in Annex E of EN 1993-1-1:2022. The ductility requirements, i.e. elongation at fracture and yield to ultimate strength ratio, are the values from the Swedish national annex to EN 1993-1-1.

Finally, protocol A covers the case of products that are traceable and for which the original documentation is available. Nondestructive hardness testing is required to affirm the properties stated in the original documentation.

Regardless of the chosen protocol, the whole assessment including data collection, condition evaluation and quality assessment is documented and gathered in an assessment report that is the basis for further processing of the products in accordance with clause 5.1 of EN 1090-2.

2.3 Implementation in practice

2.3.1 Introduction of the guidelines

In 2021 a pilot project funded by the Development Fund of the Swedish Construction Industry and initiated by a major contractor (Skanska) and a stockholder (Stena Stål), implemented the guidelines on a real case (4).

Important lessons were learned regarding practical issues such as surface preparation and analysis of the hardness results.

It was found that the member with the lower hardness value can advantageously be chosen as representative for a test unit rather than applying acceptance criteria on the variation of hardness values.

The whole assessment method was also scrutinized and approved by an independent party that was not involved in its development.

2.3.2 Current status

Similar practical experiences were made by more companies in Sweden and Norway and MVR BS04:2021 is now widely embraced by the industry.

From being considered as a potential phenomenon, steel reuse has in recent years become more common and is now often reported in the professional press as actual projects. Some examples are listed hereafter for illustration.

The supporting structure of a temporary school building in Stockholm was disassembled and its components assessed before being placed on the market as reused components, *Fig. 2 (5)*. The stockholder involved in this project has since then published an EPD dedicated to reused steel components (6). The GWP is 53 kg CO₂ eq./ton for modules A1 to A3.

Fig. 2. a) Disassembly of the structure in Stockholm; b) Reclaimed HEA300 prepared for hardness testing in Jönköping (Rival Bygg Rivning Demontering and Stena Stål).

Steel contractor EAB mixed reused and new steel in a warehouse building in Hillerstorp. The reclaimed components were initially from a manufacturing plant in Göteborg and were of common size. Those which could not directly be used were stored for upcoming projects, Fig. 3a (7). It turned out to be a building at Gislaveds Energipark Fig. 3b that could be made of 55 % reclaimed steel.

Fig. 3. a) Members in stock for future projects; b) New structure in Gislaved (EAB and Stena Stål).

Beams from Malmö's old hovercraft station were used in a new sewage treatment plant in Henriksdal, Stockholm, cutting the carbon emissions by an estimated 97%, Fig. 4 (7).

a)

b)

Fig. 4. a) Old terminal building in Malmö; b) New supports in reused steel at the treatment plant (Sweco, Tibnor and Dekra).

Traditional stockholders are the main actors who buy reclaimed components and assess their properties before selling to fabricators. There is also a place for niche companies in the broader reuse business. It has become possible for potential customers to view stocks and check the availability of reclaimed components online.

In general, the price of assessed reclaimed components is roughly the same as that of an equivalent new component. This is likely achieved by focusing on the discarded structures that are the most profitable but the assessment procedures in MVR BS04:2021 are economical enough that steel reuse could become a business opportunity.

2.3.3 Certification

Companies that deal with the assessment of reclaimed steel components can certify their assessment process but the certification is not mandatory to use or refer to MVR BS04:2021 which is in free access.

Nordcert offers a non-accredited certification based on MVR BS04:2021. It is valid for a period of five years and can be self-standing or a supplement to a certification for EN 1090-1 (8).

The target group is stockholders who intend to resell assessed components and fabricators who acquire unassessed steel.

Fabricators who simply make use of assessed components benefit indirectly from the certification as it provides an easy way to make demands on their suppliers and ensure the quality of assessment report.

The first company to receive the certification was PCS Construction AS in Norway, with an estimated monthly turnover of 20 tons reclaimed steel (9).

2.3.4 Further development

In Norway, Nordic Circles AS (10) has used MVR BS04:2021 as a basic template and adapted the methods to maritime steel from declassified ships. The hull for instance can be cut into plates that are then used in the fabrication of welded profiles. Two promising applications are sheet piling, *Fig. 5a*, and box beams (HSQ), *Fig. 5b* which are widely used to carry hollow core slabs.

Fig. 5. a) Sheet piling in reclaimed maritime steel; b) CE-marked HSQ beam (Nordic Circles AS).

The Norwegian Directorate of Public Construction and Property (*Statsbygg*) was the first customer to order box beams made of steel from an oil tanker dismantled by AF Offshore Decom in Vats. After assessment, the steel plates were used as constituent products by Skanska Stålfabrikken in the fabrication of HSQ beams and the final product could be CE-marked to EN 1090-1, see Fig. 5b. As for now, the reclaimed plates are not allowed to contain any weld seam. A reliable and economical method to assess welds and heat affected zones, would help a lot in maximizing the material output from old ships.

3 THE EUROPEAN TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION FOR REUSE

3.1 Introduction

The construction industry in Europe operates on an international market with common design and execution rules. Therefore CEN/TC135 decided in late 2021 to start working on common European recommendations for steel reuse. The task was given to CEN/TC135/WG2 which is responsible for the execution standard EN 1090-2.

The recommendations were developed as a Technical Specification (CEN/TS) rather than a European Standard (CEN/EN) which allowed for a faster process.

Contrary to EN-standards which are compulsory, it is up to the respective national standardization bodies to decide if and how a Technical Specification is to be implemented in a country.

The content of the CEN/TS was adopted by CEN/TC135 in September 2023 and finalized as FprCEN/TS 1090-201:2024 in April 2024. It is now submitted to formal vote by the national committees with closure in July and expected for publication in September.

The recommendations and methods in the Technical Specification were based on available national guidelines (11; 12; 13; 14; 15; 16; 17) and the findings (18) and recommendations (19) from the RFCS-project PROGRESS.

In the following we highlight the main differences between CEN/TS and MVR BS04:2021 and explain the background for these differences.

3.2 The scope of CEN/TS 1090-201

The scope of the CEN/TS was initially limited to the execution of structures to EXC2 in order to implicitly prohibit the use of reclaimed products in structures prone to fatigue. It was however argued that EXC3 does not always imply fatigue loading but is a requirement for many statically loaded structures thus placing unnecessary restraint to reuse.

The scope was therefore extended to even include EXC3 and reformulated to emphasize that reclaimed products should only be used for quasi static loading and not when fatigue design is required.

The applicability in case of seismic loading was not extensively discussed at the European level but left to the national standardization committees.

The assessment of reclaimed products starts with a reusability assessment that applies to both reclaimed structural components, i.e. fabricated products, and constituent products, i.e. sections.

The quality assessment which results in the declaration of the relevant properties listed in clause 5.1 of EN 1090-2:2018+A1:2024 applies to plates, hot-rolled profiles and hot finished or cold formed hollow sections in carbon steel used as constituent products.

The quality assessment can also be applied to base material of fabricated products but it does not include the assessment of connections and is thus incomplete.

The scope of the CEN/TS is thus the same as MVR BS04:2021 with the inclusion of EXC3.

There is an ambition to extend the assessment to fabricated products but the recommendations with regard to corrosion protection systems and connections are so far only given as informative annexes and will need to be further developed in the future.

3.3 Reusability assessment

The rules for condition evaluation are more elaborated in CEN/TS and open for the reuse of more products.

In particular, it is possible to reuse products which do not meet the essential tolerances in EN 1090-2 if the deviations are correctly declared and accounted for in the design. This applies to local damages.

Also reclaimed products that have been exposed to fire may be reused if their characteristic yield strength does not exceed S355.

On the other hand, stricter rules are introduced with regard to hollow sections. The longitudinal welds need to be visually inspected along their whole length to ensure no surface breaking defects. And for products manufactured before 1970, the weld seam should be entirely inspected with nondestructive testing (MPI or UT).

3.4 Quality assessment

3.4.1 General

The general principles for quality assessment are the same in CEN/TS as in MVR BS04:2021: it relies on grouping in test units and a combination of nondestructive and destructive testing. The four protocols A to D as well as the flowchart presented in *Fig. 1* are still valid.

However, modern and older steels are now defined as type 1 respective type 2 structural steels and the cut-off year is set as 1970 instead of 1971. It can then be assumed that type 1 structural steel has a set of relevant properties, including their variations, equivalent to one of the standard materials listed in EN 1993-1-1:2022.

Protocol A, i.e. when documentation is available, is simplified as hardness testing is no longer required.

Protocol B, i.e. for type 1 steel, is essentially unchanged but the material properties can either be declared directly as characteristic properties derived from test results or by reference to an equivalent steel grade.

In order to derive the characteristic values from a single test it can be assumed that the coefficients of variation of yield and ultimate strength are known and equal to the values given in Annex E of EN 1993-1-1:2022.

The same approach was already found in MVR BS04:2021 and SCI P427 (13), as well as the recommendations from ECCS (19).

3.4.2 Impact toughness

If required, the impact toughness should be tested and declared accordingly. According to MVR BS04:2021 a subgrade JR could be assumed without testing for all steels produced after 1946. CEN/TS is more conservative in that regard and limits this simplification to type 1 steel, i.e. produced in or after 1970.

3.4.3 Heat delivery condition

CEN/TS is more cautious with regard to the heat delivery condition which affects the design of hollow sections. It states plainly that the cold formed condition should be assumed if no clearer information is available. This is a conservative assumption.

3.5 Simplified assumptions

CEN/TS opens for simplified assumptions which do not require destructive material testing. For use in execution class EXC1, components with known provenance manufactured after 1990 may be assumed to be S235JR.

The same assumption is found in MVR BS04:2021 where it can be applied to EXC2 and steel as old as 1946. It is an appropriate method for simple constructions or where the stiffness rather than the strength is driving the design.

In CEN/TS, the limitation to EXC1 will rule out most practical cases.

Furthermore, if the product is to be welded – which normally can be assumed – the chemical composition should be determined by destructive testing anyway.

Overall, it can be concluded that, for all practical purposes, CEN/TS does not permit reuse based on simplified assumptions and without testing.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Steel reuse has in the past few years become a much more common occurrence in Sweden and Norway. Integrated reuse, where reclaimed products are used as constituent products and combined with new material if necessary appears to be a successful strategy.

Assessment methods could be developed that combine the right amount of non-destructive and destructive testing based on available data and provide the information required by the execution standard EN 1090-2.

MVR BS04:2021 was well received by the industry. It clarifies what should be expected from reclaimed products, constitutes a quality assurance, inclusive the possibility of a certification, and fits within the regulatory framework for steel structures.

CEN/TS 1090-201 will be a common base for the assessment of reclaimed steel products in Europe. It is in principle very similar to MVR BS04:2021 and will only introduce minor changes that should be easy to implement in a Swedish context.

With increasing trust, the demand for reclaimed products is now greater than the available amount of material and there is a strong incentive to widen the scope of the assessment, fabrication and design methods in order to reuse more product types that are excluded today: steel from other sources than building, e.g. maritime steel, welded products and products with minor defects.

CEN/TS 1090-201 already includes some guidance for the reuse of fabricated products in informative annexes. This should be investigated further. The assessment of welds is of particular interest.

CEN/TS 1090-201 allows deviations from essential tolerances provided that they are documented and accounted for in the design. This calls for adapted design models not readily available.

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